

The Use of Natural Dye Plants in East Nusa Tenggara

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ABSTRACT

Traditional fabric has historical and cultural value among East Nusa Tenggara (ENT) community livelihood. That can be seen by the uses of traditional clothes as uniform on civil servant and as important matter on traditional procession. The uses of plant as dye source still carry out by some waver group. Research on natural dye is important to support traditional waver. The research starts with identification plant species, measure density of dye plants and its spread. Ethnobotanical study exploration, and vegetation analysis method was used. The result showed that There are tree species of plant that act as main ingredients which are Nila (*Indigofera* sp.) as blue to black color source, Mengkudu (*Morinda* sp.) as orange to red color source, and Loba (*Symplocos* sp.) as mordant source. Three species of that plant fund widespread almost in ENT region except for Loba. Loba fund only in Sumba and Flores region with trees density 15,33 tree/ha. *Morinda* was fund with trees density 19.67 tree/ha. While *Indigofera* fund almost everywhere with trees density 1000 tree/ha. The process of making fabric woven from yarn spinning to finishing takes 2-6 months, so that reasonable if the price in the local market average of 2 million rupiahs apiece, even commercially abroad and at the island of Bali prices reached 3.5 million to 6 million rupiahs/sheets. As for the needs to be pursued at the moment is to guide weaving made from natural and find solutions to the market so indirectly will help improve the welfare of the community.

Keywords: Traditional fabric, natural dyes, trees density

1. INTRODUCTION

East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) is an island province which has a rich variety of vegetation types typical of semi-dry climate and the potential to be developed to encourage an increase in regional income areas. Based on NTT Provincial Forestry Office report (2007), on the island of Timor there are no less 544 types of vegetation and trees and shrubs there are 29 types of non-timber forest products that includes the fruit, seeds, gums, essential oils, scented wood, honey, shellac products to medicinal plants and natural dyes.

During this Kupang Forestry Research Institute has found 14 species of plants producing dyes from the area of East Sumba, Ende, and South Central Timor. Data distribution of the dye-producing plants previously demonstrated in the three counties, four species found in East Sumba has Mengkudu, Indigo, Yellow Wood and Soga. 10 species in Ende, among others: Mengkudu, Nila, Lo'ba, Wood yellow, Maketaki, Areca nut, Ketapang, Salombo, candle nut, and pacar tree while at TTU there are 5 types, namely, Noni, Nila, Arbila, Kesambi, and Nobah. Dye above are divided into two groups seen in its usefulness. First is the group of basic dyes are producing mengkudu roots of red, yellow wood-producing skin yellow, and blue color-producing leaves Nila. Process compounding basic color components will produce different colors, including green and black. The second group is in addition to the above types of reinforcing material/color support (Handoko *et al.*, 2004).

The existence of the community fabric production unit ENT is the fact. Statistics of East Sumba in 2001 showed there were approximately 3013 units of forbic production, while

according to Statistics of TTU there were 357 units in 2003 and Statistics of Ende noted there were 9375 units. Given the magnitude of the potential of existing natural resources, it would require excavation potential flagship species of local plants to be able to provide alternative livelihoods for the community.

The purpose of this research is to conduct a study botany study, the identification and inventory of the potential and use of various types of natural dye-producing plants in East Nusa Tenggara. Objectives of this study was obtained data and information on the types of dye-producing plants include aspects of botany study, plant species, distribution, potential.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Botany Study

Extracting information about the type, used parts, and plant utilization by the community in an area done by way of structured interviews (with guide) and an open questionnaire. Respondents consisted of indigenous shamans and artisans/weavers of cloth and fabric sales dealer.

2.2 Exploration

Estimation of potential and distribution of flora producing dyes using census and sampling methods (plot measurement). Census method used to determine the potential for other types of dye-producing plants outside the forest area and its potential is limited then made a point of recording the coordinate distribution of flora. While the sampling method used when the flora is identified in the area of forest area or if the potential distribution in the wild is estimated to spread evenly. The broad swath of each measure to the growth rate is as follows:

- *Seedlings* is from germination to high 1.5 m Measuring Permanent Plots (MPP) 2x2m
- *Saplings* is regeneration growth rate that reached a high of 1.5 meters with a trunk diameter of less than 10 cm MPP 5x5 m
- *Poles* is rate of growth of young trees with a trunk diameter measuring between 10-19 cm (dbh) with MPP 10 x 10 m
- *Trees* is level of trees with stem diameters above 20 cm dbh.

2.3 Data Analysis

Qualitative data from botany study survey described in descriptive analysis, such as how to use and the parts used parts, etc. The use of dose. Vegetation data have been collected and then analyzed to determine the density of the type, relative density, dominance type, relative dominance, frequency type, relative frequency and importance value index. Vegetation data analysis results are discussed to conclude the status of the availability and characteristics of these plants in nature.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Botany Study and Potential

The study botany study in the field is to gather information related to the dye-producing plant species commonly used by people either past or the type that are still used. As for the types of plants that get by district and parts used are presented in Table 1.

Tabel 1. Type and utilization of plants as natural dyes.

Site (District)	Species	Used Part	Color resulting	Density (per ha)
Rote Ndao (S10 53.492 E122 49.297)	Indigofera	Leaf	Black, green	433.3
	Morinda	Root	red	5.32
	Tamarin	Root and seed	Scarlet/ yern fasteners	1.25
	Orchid	Stem and leaf	Adhesive and yern cleaning	-
	Turmeric	Rumpang	Yello	-
Sabu Raijua (S10 30.019 E121 50.306)	Indigofera	Leaf	Bleck, green	366.7
	Morinda	Root/root bark	Red	20
	Sterculia	Shell	Mordan black color	13.75
Larantuka (S8 17.441 E122 58.363)	Indigofera	Leaf	Black, green	66.7
	Morinda	Root/root bark	Red	33.69
	Kashew	Stem bark	Brown	36
	Menggo	Leaf	Green/black	2.5
	Kenila	Stem bark	Brown	4
	Cactus	Fruit	Red	700
	Yello wood	Stem	Yello	20.62
Sesbania	Leaf	green	3	

This type of cloth dye plants can be grouped into the main material, and material anointment mordant / amplifier, where the types of materials used to assist the process of mordanting usually contain salt, chromium hydroxide, aluminum or tin. The division of the resulting material is classified into two that is eternal and temporary/can wear off.

3.2 Utilization of Plant Material as a Natural Dyes

Different types of plants usually have one part used as a source of natural dyes. As illustrated in table 1 above, parts of which can be utilized as a source of dyes in the form of leaves, bark (pepagan), fruits, stems and roots.

3.2.1 Nila

Plants Nila (*Indigofera tinctoria*) is often known by other names Tauk (Rote) Taum (Timor, Flores), Tarum (Sunda) tom (Java) Noba (Sabu). This plant is included in the tribe of legumes or Fabaceae) is a plant producing blue / black natural. The use of clothing dyes is mainly done in the manufacture of woven rope in some districts in ENT. Tarum used for producing blue / black, indigo blue color is obtained from the marinade leaves (in quantity) for one night or more. After overnight will form a layer on top of a green or blue.

Each region has different ways and methods in use and gathering of these plants to produce the desired color. On the island of Rote and Sabu to make this plant to produce the color black / blue is by soaking the leaves for 3 days and then crushed to pieces. From leaves that had been destroyed along this water will be generated which is then precipitated in the form of pasta pasta is utilized to perform soaking yarn by adding new water and whiting (oxide) for one night then wind dried for 1 day. To produce a blue color is usually soaking and draining as the above step is usually performed only dive 3 times and to be able to produce the black color is usually soaked up to 5-8 times. While people in Larantuka (East Flores) did not do that to produce pasta soaking but soaking the leaves will be done in order to produce a solution of indigo, black and of course this solution can directly be used to make yarn immersion by adding whiting by about 1 tablespoon per 5 liters of water.

3.2.2 Mengkudu

Morinda (*Morinda citrifolia* L.) kelurik: Floreses, morinda Javanese: pace, kemudu, kudu. Sundanese language; cengkudu : Maduraese kodhuk. Balinese language: wengkudu) is a plant that originated from Southeast Asia. This plant grows in the lowlands to the altitude of 1,500 meters above sea permukaan. Addition has been used as a medicinal plant, Mengkudu can also dimanfaatkan also used as a dye used to give color to the fabric weaving, batik or woven from pandanus. *Morinda* root bark can be used as a colorant because it contains compounds that provide morindon Morindin and red and yellow.

Use of material in the form of root bark for making cloth colored red or brown. Making process is also similar to that in other colors. However, the weavers usually know which ones measure used to determine the composition of color. Society typically uses noni comparison between the skin which has become a powder with a ratio of 1: 4, in which every 1 kg of Noni can be used to color the 4 kg of yarn.

3.2.3 Yellow Wood

Yellow Wood (*Cudrania conchinchinensis*) scattered at an altitude of 100-1800 above the mean sea level (AMSL), and gather in certain locations or near sources of water. While handling a dyes is with the use of roots and stems by cutting the roots and stems. Roots and stems that have been cut and then boiled $\pm$ 2 hours / until the resulting solution was yellow, then let it cool. To do is to do a yarn dyeing yarn soaking in a solution of distillate boiling solution of the yellow wood that has been filtered and warmed again. Soaking time required for one night to produce a yellow color, while for better results can be repeated until the desired color is formed. The trees not cultivated because its growth is very slow and its utilization as natural dyes in batik / weaving is rarely even is not used anymore.

3.2.4 Cashew

Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) commonly cultivated to take the beans, cashew Cashew trees can also be used as firewood or as low-quality building materials. This tree has also been widely planted in the garden as shade trees or plants as well as rehabilitation of marginal land. The bark of cashew tree can be used for tanning and gives a dark brown color. Cashew commonly found in East Flores Regency, where the goal is to fill cultivation sleep and less productive land or gardens residents. To use natural dyes derived from the bark of this tree is very little because according to the information society, the resulting material is not very resistant to faded and irradiation when compared with the use of mengkudu. For the process of its utilization is by boiling bark materials as much as 3/4 pot on a fully charged water for 2 hours over medium heat. Wait until warm and lift the existing timber, then enter the material of thread that will color for one night and drain. Residual water can be reused until the appropriate color as desired sharpness.

3.2.5 Knila

Knila (*Peltophorum inerme* (Roxb.) in Larantuka (Adonara) called Laru trees, in Sabu Raijua and people of Timor island is also called the wood with Laru trees. Besides the above functions the wood bark can be used as a dyes that will produce the color orange. Here is the wood that has been used as Laru trees dyes by people in Adonara Island East Flores district. in the world of natural dyes for this piece of wood bark Laru trees in use as a producer of tanning substances, which are commonly used as Ubar (dye) nets . the colors can be produced by this the plant is brownish red or orange. On the island of Sabu the plant is also known by the name Laru trees, where the bark used as a mixture to strengthen the green or black color that is mixed together with the leaf *indigofera*. In Larantuka bark also used as a fabric dye which will produce a red/orange, which distinguishes its function with the use on the island of Sabu is situated on the

intended use. as the main raw material, in Larantuka laru trees bark used in a way to boil for 2 hours then allowed to stand for 1 night. the next step is to separate the water in the skin by filtered, filtered water is then used as material to soak the cotton yarn which has been prepared.

The results of estimation are performed using a pan in diameter 40 cm and height 60 cm weavers use to boil the bark weighing 8kg, with as many as 8 liter filled with water, after boiling for 2 hours to spare $\pm$ 3.5 liters of water. With 3.5 liters of water can be used to soak the yarn weighing 1.7 kg, soaked for 1 night. Soaking can be done 2-4 times to produce the desired color. While the rest of the bark can be boiled first boiling it back up to a maximum of 4 times.

3.2.6 Turmeric

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* Linn. Syn. *Curcuma domestica* Val.) Tuber roots older than one year is used as a substitute bright yellow color. Parts to be used should be selected sections of old and hard, resulting in optimal color. Information obtained when using a forced hiatus material that is still young so the resulting color will fade quickly and easily fade.

3.2.7 Turi

Turi (*Sesbania grandiflora* syn.) Is a small tree (height reaches 10m). Local names in Indonesian include turi (Javanese), Scientific Classification: Kingdom Plantae Division Magnoliophyta, class Magnoliopsida, Order Fabales, Fabaceae Family, Nation Robinieae, Genus Sesbania. Part of the turi used as dyes is a leaf, which will produce a light green color. The results of studies conducted in Larantuka botany study is an innovation/or experiment conducted by a weaver, known as Mrs. Bota. There are special from the experiments performed in used turi ie if most of the utilization of a particular plant parts are supported by the use of other types, but at the leaf turi not mixed with any kind so that the resulting color is very young green or almost whitish.

3.3 The Process of Making Black

How to process the leaves tauk/which will produce natural colors made by the community Ndao Rote and Sabu Larantuka and Sikka district have in common but the community in Flores prefers to thread in *Indigofera* soaking that has been oxidized by immersion for 3-5 days directly. First leaf separated tauk leaves and stems then immersed into ordinary water with a ratio of 1:8 (1 kg of indigo soaked in 8 liters of water) for 3-5 days with plain water in the bucket/barrel, after that squeeze/shake until frothy, remove leaves from the bucket, and the solution is ready for use as an ingredient of immersion. Prior to immersion-spun yarn, water present in the mix with lime and ash as much as each 1 tablespoon/handheld. The next process is carried out is to soak the spun yarn into the water together for 3 days. To get a good black color, proceed as above until 5 times, where the distance between the immersion done draining until the yarn in the dry state.

So that staining could be more durable and does not fade due to washing or drying process, usually weavers in Rote Ndao using sand mud around the lake or reservoir sites. Sludge containing high iron levels. Usually the sludge is taken and mixed with some kind of fabric together with a choice of colors. After being mixed and stirred, with the condition of the cloth in the mud soaking is left overnight. Besides durable, the use of mud to sand is also produced visible color so bright and strong motifs depicted on the cloth clearly visible as well.

3.4 The Process of Making Green

The green color can be generated from the process of Soaking the plant materials like leaves Taum / indigo. As for the manufacturing process similar to the process of making black but if the black color made in generating immersion served until 5 times then to produce a green color only takes 2-3 times of immersion. Any thread that has been soaked in drying is not done directly under the blazing sun, but the best is by the dry wind the string. There are several things

that affect the absorption of the color of the yarn are the type of yarn used and the viscosity of the solution used.

Water used for the same amount of green staining by immersion using the color green which is 1:8. The image of indigo soaking is ready for use are as follows.

Figure 1: a. The results of the indigo soaking is ready for use; b. The thread that is ready to be soaked with a solution of indigo; c. Immersion results indigo yarn

Difficulties encountered during soaking and draining is less strong rope or raffia leaves so that the solution Tarum gebang into yarn ties. Result of the the inclusion colored water into the bond would cause the pattern to be in the form of a broken and irregular which will lead to lower prices when marketing.

3.5 The Process of Making Red

In the process of making red, at Sikka and East Flores Regency materials used is similar to the process undertaken by the islands of Rote and Sabu, Rote and Sabu if the people do pulverization root of *Morinda citrifolia* roots that is cleaned, crushed, boiled until boiling, after this process will produce a red solution. However, people in Larantuka and Maumere not using Noni roots will directly but uses skin from *Morinda* roots. To form the desired pattern, prepare a yarn that will be given a red color and soak in the solution for three days, after which it will be removed spun yarn spun yarns produced originally white will become red. Here is a picture of the roots of *Morinda citrifolia* and Laru trees skin and thread the immersion.

a

b

c

d

Figure 2: a. The Roots of Morinda; b. Powdered root of Morinda skin; c. Immersion of the roots of Morinda threads; d. Yarn stretching Morinda root immersion results

The use of materials such as roots to make a red or brown colored fabric. Making process is also similar to that in other colors. However, the weavers usually know which ones measure used to determine the composition of color. Society typically uses Morinda comparison between the skin which has become a powder with a ratio of 1: 4, in which every 1 kg of Morinda can be used to color the 4 kg of yarn. While the use of open-mouthed as an ingredient in red mordanting with a ratio of 1: 40, where every 1kg of skin/greedy leaves can be used to mix as much as 40 kg of yarn.

3.6 The Process of Making Orange/Brown

In the world of natural dyes for these plants that can produce color brown / orange is the Laru wood bark and a few relatives *Leguminosaceae* in use as a producer of tanning substances, which are commonly used as Ubar (dye) nets. The colors can be generated by this the plant is brownish red or orange. As the main raw material, in Lantuka Lru trees used in a way to boil for 2 hours then allowed to stand for 1 night. The next step is to separate the water with the skin to by filtered, filtered water is then used as material to soak the cotton yarn which has been prepared.

The results of estimation are performed using a pan in diameter 40 cm and height 60 cm weavers use to boil the bark weighing 8kg, with as much as 8 liters of water filled, after boiling for 2 hours to spare $\pm$ 3.5 liters of water. With 3.5 liters of water can be used to soak the yarn

weighing 1.7 kg, soaked for 1 night. Soaking can be done 2-4 times to produce the desired color. While the rest of the bark can be boiled first boiling it back up to a maximum of 4 times.

3.7 Measuring The Quality of The Dye on The Fabric and Yarn

The quality of a dye in the fabric/yarn can be assessed from several aspects, such as: resistance to sunlight (fading), flexibility and resistance to washing/response to the stains that come from other objects. The purpose of this test is to determine the extent and durability kelunturan fading in the yarn and fabric dyed using several types of plants. While the results of testing the quality of yarn is done in the Faculty of Engineering, Islamic University of Indonesia are as follows:

Table 2. Test results thread to sunlight

Species of plant	Fastness Value Against Sunlight	fade Value Against the Laundering	Value Defamation
<i>Peltophorum inerme</i> Roxb.	3-4 (quite good)	3-4 (quite good)	4 (good)
<i>Morinda</i> sp.	4-5 (good)	3-4 (quite good)	1 (poor)
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	4-5 (quite good)	3-4 (quite good)	1 (poor)
<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn	4-5 (good)	3-4 (quite good)	1 (poor)
<i>Indigofera</i> sp.	5 (good)	3-4 (quite good)	3 (rather)
Woven fabric	4 (good)	3 (rather)	1-2 (poor)
<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i>	3-4 (quite good)	3-4 (quite good)	4 (good)

The results of analysis carried out showed that *Peltophorum inerme* Roxb. has a value of fastness to washing and drying well against adequate good sunlight while *Morinda* bad at the time of leaching. Taum which is a type of dye that has a color eternity has good resistance to irradiation and washing does not cause bleeding on the other fabrics are washed together.

3.8 Chemical Content of Natural Dyes

Each plant species has a different content. From a variety of active ingredients is then be used for various purposes including to dye cloth. The chemical content of the main ingredients of natural dyes contained in the the plant results in esplorasi Rote, Sabu, Sikka, and Larantuka were as follows:

Table 3. Chemical content of natural dyes

Species	Matter	Color	Function	Color component
<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i>	Fresh leaf	Blue, Black	Dyes	<i>Indirubin</i>
<i>Morinda</i> sp.	Root	Red	Dyes	<i>Morindin</i>
<i>Symplocos cochinchinensis</i>	Fall leaf	Red	Mordant	<i>Aluminium kelat</i> ($Al-(R)_3$)
<i>Opuntia cochientilifera</i>	Fruit	Orange	Dyes	<i>Diocetyl phthalate</i>
<i>Cudrania conchinchinensis</i>	Bark	Yello	Dyes	<i>Cycloartanyl acetate</i>

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Fabrics produced from natural dyes have broad market prospects abroad, while in Indonesia itself is still used for ceremonial equipment, clothes and dress gloves, bag, sampler, accessory. If during this community using *symplocos* by peeling the skin, the test Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrum showed that the levels of aluminum kalat of the *Symplocos* leaves as high as the skin so that the old leaves can be used as a skin substitute. Yarns and fabrics made using natural materials have properties more resistant to sunlight, discolored and stained by other material risks are better than the fabric resulting from chemical dyes. As for the needs to be pursued at the moment is to guide weaving made from natural and find solutions to the market so indirectly will help improve the welfare of the community.

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PREFACE

“Society is the ultimate beneficiary of research”. This statement means that all the result of research activities should be equally distributed to all users and stakeholders. There are many tools to disseminate research findings, and one of them is through a scientific conference. Its role as a media for researchers and users includes policy-makers to cooperate closely to understand specific needs, ensure relevance of topics, and improve communication, dissemination and implementation of the research recommendations makes scientific conference essential to any research agency.

The International Conference of Indonesia Forestry Researchers (INAFOR) was an endeavour of Forestry Research and Development Agency (FORDA), the Ministry of Forestry to actively improve the quality of Indonesian forestry research and publications as well as establish a robust scientific forum for Indonesia forestry professionals from research and development entities including government agencies, private sectors and universities. Its first event was conducted in 5-7 December 2011 in Bogor under the theme of **“Strengthening Forest Science and Technology for Better Forestry Development”**.

This conference aimed to provide international experience for Indonesia forestry researchers, and develop forestry research and development activities in Indonesia. In regards to international forestry research forum, the International Union of Forest Research Organizations (IUFRO) involved numerous Indonesian participants. Unfortunately, this impressive complicity has failed to be redeemed by numbers of accepted papers. This mainly due to lack of experience in international conference mechanism and less technical knowledge in preparing the drafts.

This proceeding is a documentation and publication of papers and posters presented in the conference. It consist of 110 succesfully presented oral presentations and 77 papers out of 110 oral presentation have been selected to be sent to IUFRO forum. I expect this publication could be distributed to all participants, users, partners and other stakeholders throughout Indonesia.

In addition, I would like to acknowledge all the authors of papers and posters contributed in this proceeding. The comments and review from the editors towards the publishing of the proceeding are also greatly appreciated. I am also grateful for the participants who had actively involved in the conference. Finally, I wish this proceeding and the conference could contribute endless benefits to the society toward strengthening forest science and technology for better forestry development.

Jakarta, November 2012

Director General of FORDA

Dr. R. Iman Santoso

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“Strengthening Forest Science and Technology for Better Forestry Development”

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